

ISic0711

I.Sicily inscription 0711

Language

Latin

Type

funerary;

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.20.10

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

From the necropolis found c.1960 on via Dottor Consoli / via
Androne

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. [-]Seius Agatho
2. [- - -]LMN.II semis de
3. [- - -]tio die m. Ianuarii

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493947

EDCS 32701134

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 46 n.226

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fig.48

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 28 no.100

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